

CLUSTER TYPES AND ORGANIZATION OF THE PROCESSES OF LESSONS DEDICATED TO NATIONAL CRAFTS FROM TECHNOLOGY SCIENCE BASED ON THEM

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Abstract. *In this article, first of all, the content and types of the cluster approach were discussed in order to highlight the significant importance of the cluster approach in the educational process. After that, it touched on the issues of organizing lesson processes dedicated to national crafts based on the cluster and its types.*

Keywords: *cluster approach, cluster types, technology lessons, "visual brainstorming", national crafts.*

It is known from history that the goal of achieving high efficiency in educational processes was set, and based on this, different approaches and methods were used in each lesson. Even today, this tradition has not lost its essence in the educational system. While staying true to the tradition, currently in the organization of technology lessons (labor education), in particular, in providing students with information about national crafts It should be noted that various methods and approaches are used to arouse interest in national handicrafts in them, to meaningfully organize lesson processes dedicated to national handicrafts. As one of such approaches, it is possible to give an example of the cluster approach, first of all, it is appropriate to dwell on the main content of this approach and what types of it there are, and only then, on the basis of these types, to focus on the issues of organizing lesson processes dedicated to national handicrafts.

In various methodological sources, this method is given different names: "concept map", "schema map", "hedgehog", "associogram", etc. Going deeper into the essence of the approach, a cluster is one that allows students to think freely about a topic, access their knowledge, understanding, or ideas about a particular topic, as well as memory and it can be understood that it is a pedagogical strategy that develops spatial thinking. This strategy can be done individually, in groups, or as a whole class. It should also be said that the cluster is a flexible and multifunctional method that can be used at all stages of the lesson to learn, reinforce, repeat and control a new topic. This is a graphic organization of material on a certain topic, which allows you to imagine the thought processes that occur when entering it. It is also said to be the opposite of a non-linear form of cluster thinking. Sometimes this method is called "visual brainstorming". Acceptance of clusters is universal. It can be used to systematize existing information and identify areas of sufficient knowledge during the *call* phase. At the thinking stage, the cluster allows you to get fragments of new information. At the thinking stage, concepts are grouped and logical connections are established between them.

It is also necessary to pay attention to the essence of the adoption of technology organized on the basis of the cluster approach: to distinguish the semantic units of the subject and their graphic design in a certain order in the form of a "stack" - a diagram. One of the most important

aspects is distinguishing the main semantic unit, that is, a specific topic in technology lessons; highlighting semantic units associated with the keyword (categories of information within the subject); considering accuracy with facts and opinions.

Now on the basis of above information it was considered permissible to dwell in more detail on the issues of paying attention to the important aspects of using the cluster approach in the organization of technology lessons and organizing lesson processes mainly dedicated to national handicrafts in a content-rich form based on the effective use of the cluster approach and its types.

The clustering system allows for too much information to be covered. Therefore, it is necessary to analyze the cluster formed in the work after covering a new topic in the lessons aimed at teaching national handicrafts as a "field of ideas" and determine the directions of development of the topic.

In some cases, it is necessary to allow for the following cases or options in the lessons of the national crafts of the technology classes, these are: elaborating on the topic (if necessary) identifying a few key points to focus on; clustering is used both in the challenge stage and in the reflection stage, it can be a method of stimulating mental activity before learning the topic or a form of systematization of information based on the results of the transfer of the material.

Depending on the purpose of these practical lessons, the teacher organizes individual independent work or collective activities of students in the form of a general joint discussion. It is no secret that the subject area is wide, that is, it is not limited. Therefore, clusters can be used not only to arouse or further develop students' interest in national crafts, but also to study various topics.

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